

Technical Note

HyperCoreg: An Automated, Operational Pipeline for Co-Registering PRISMA and EnMAP Hyperspectral Imagery

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Abstract

HyperCoreg is an automated, end-to-end pipeline for geometric co-registration of spaceborne hyperspectral imagery (PRISMA L2D and EnMAP L2A) to Sentinel-2 Level-2A reference data. The workflow addresses scene-dependent geolocation errors that hinder reliable data fusion and multi-temporal analyses, particularly in cloud-affected acquisitions. HyperCoreg builds on the AROSICS framework without replacing its image-matching engine and extends it at the workflow level through four operational functions: automated Sentinel-2 candidate selection, hyperspectral-to-multispectral band pairing, sequential alignment logic, and quality-controlled acceptance. The main output is a co-registered hyperspectral cube along with comprehensive metrics, per-scene reports, and optional diagnostic products that support accessible quality control. Performance is evaluated on a long time series of PRISMA images collected from 2019 to 2025 and an EnMAP test set acquired in 2025, over the Metropolitan City of Rome (Italy). The multi-sensor dataset encompasses heterogeneous acquisition conditions, including variable cloud cover, illumination, and seasonal variability. The results show systematic reductions in mean residual error compared with a controlled basic AROSICS-based pipeline configuration. The largest gains are achieved in challenging conditions where tie points are sparse or unevenly distributed. By improving geometric consistency, this pipeline facilitates spatial layering and integration of hyperspectral data with higher-resolution urban layers and supports a range of downstream applications where data integration and spatiotemporal consistency are cornerstones of further analysis.

Keywords: remote sensing; hyperspectral imaging; image co-registration; data integration; PRISMA; EnMAP; Sentinel-2; AROSICS; multi-temporal analysis

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1. Introduction

The increasing availability of spaceborne hyperspectral optical imagery is enabling new applications in environmental monitoring, geology, agriculture, and urban studies [1]. However, hyperspectral imagery is often affected by residual geolocation inaccuracies that vary across sensors and acquisition conditions [2]. In many operational and research workflows, hyperspectral products must be co-registered to improve geolocation, which is a prerequisite for accurate integration with ancillary data sources and consistent multi-temporal comparability [3].

Recent hyperspectral missions such as PRISMA (PRecursore IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa; [4–6]) and EnMAP (Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program; [7])

provide rich spectral information, but depending on the geographic location of the acquisition, their products frequently require additional geolocation refinement to minimize the spatial mismatch between the pixel and field element representation. Co-registration methods are widely available, with the most basic approach being the visual inspection and linking among images of clearly identifiable ground features. Nevertheless, co-registration remains a challenging task when many scenes over the same area of interest are considered, as each scene can present different conditions (variable cloud cover, different levels of heterogeneity among land-cover types). Therefore, processing parameters often must be chosen and adapted accordingly. The technical challenge that this paper aims to address inherently relates to a spatial data management problem. The main benefit achievable with the proposed solution is that it facilitates the required pre-processing of multi-sensor hyperspectral remote sensing images, so that they can then be spatially analyzed with other geospatial data.

To address these limitations, the research community has developed dedicated co-registration algorithms. One of the best known is AROSICS (Automated and robust open-source image co-registration software, version 1.13.2; [8,9]), a Python 3.12.4-based open-source software including an easy-to-use user interface for automatic detection and correction of sub-pixel misalignments between various remote sensing datasets. Gefolki [10] is another free and open-source Python package that implements a Lucas–Kanade Iterative algorithm based on optical flow computation. The availability of these tools stimulated their use by other researchers in the framework of dedicated image processing and analytical workflows [11–13]. Furthermore, other co-registration methods have been developed and tested [3,14].

However, the above tools have been used almost exclusively on single-sensor datasets and not yet extensively on long time series of hyperspectral satellite imagery encompassing a wide range of cloud cover conditions. Given that researchers can now access images collected by various hyperspectral satellite missions, and thus compose multi-sensor datasets to undertake their investigations, co-registration pipelines must support reliable image processing under such conditions. While most studies usually rely only on fully cloud-free images (thus discarding images with clouds) acquired at given latitudes or under specific seasonal conditions, such stringent requirements must be relaxed in order to perform the intended analysis. Furthermore, for some observation and monitoring purposes, even partially cloud-covered images are suitable for analysis because the image portion of interest is sufficiently cloud-free and visible. Therefore, the gap to be addressed is the lack of an operational, quality-controlled workflow for large multi-sensor hyperspectral time series.

To support these application scenarios and add workflow-level functions beyond existing tools, HyperCoreg was developed as an automated and operational pipeline for the co-registration of PRISMA and EnMAP imagery to Sentinel-2 reference data. HyperCoreg is built on the AROSICS framework [9]. HyperCoreg does not replace the AROSICS image-matching engine; rather, its contribution is the integration of workflow-level extensions around that core. These extensions consist of automated Sentinel-2 candidate selection, hyperspectral-to-multispectral band pairing, sequential alignment logic, and quality-controlled acceptance, which together address the practical need for reliable and reproducible co-registration across heterogeneous scenes. The pipeline is designed to operate in both single-scene and batch mode through transparent parameterization and report creation. Accordingly, the contribution is positioned as a geospatial data-processing workflow that supports the preparation of analysis-ready hyperspectral layers for subsequent spatial and multi-temporal analysis, rather than as a new standalone image-matching algorithm.

This technical note is structured as follows: (i) Sections 2.1–2.6 describe the HyperCoreg methodology, including system architecture, data processing, Sentinel-2 ref-

erence acquisition, co-registration, geometric transformation, and quality assessment; (ii) Sections 2.7–2.9 present the pipeline outputs, hardware and computational requirements, and baseline configuration; and (iii) Sections 2.10 and 3 describe the testing dataset and the results of the performance assessment. The performance of HyperCoreg is assessed on a long time series of PRISMA images collected from 2019 to 2025 and an EnMAP test set acquired in 2025, over the Metropolitan City of Rome (Italy). Because the considered scenes vary in complexity, they allow for the comparison of mean residual co-registration errors achieved from the full HyperCoreg workflow and from a controlled basic AROSICS-based pipeline retaining the AROSICS-based registration core while excluding selected HyperCoreg enhancement steps.

2. Materials and Methods

This section details the HyperCoreg processing workflow and its configurable settings. The pipeline generates a co-registered hyperspectral cube as the main output, alongside optional diagnostic and ancillary products further explained in Section 2.7.2. In addition, HyperCoreg compiles per-scene reports and machine-readable metrics to support transparent quality assessment and reproducible batch processing. Key parameters controlling candidate selection, registration acceptance, and output generation are described in Section 2.2. The following subsections describe the individual modules and the resulting output products in detail.

2.1. System Architecture and Data Processing

HyperCoreg is implemented as a modular architecture designed to process hyperspectral satellite imagery from the PRISMA and EnMAP missions. The pipeline consists of five main modules:

- Data processing;
- Sentinel-2 reference acquisition;
- Co-registration (global and local);
- Geometric transformation;
- Quality assessment.

The full workflow implemented by HyperCoreg is summarized in Figure 1. The color coding highlights the HyperCoreg additions compared to AROSICS.

The co-registration core is based on the AROSICS framework, which implements automated image matching through phase correlation and local tie-point detection [8,15]. Input hyperspectral data include PRISMA Level-2D products and EnMAP Level-2A products. Image matching and tie-point extraction therefore rely on AROSICS, whereas HyperCoreg contributes the surrounding operational logic for reference discovery and ranking, sensor-specific preparation, hyperspectral-to-multispectral band pairing, VNIR/SWIR branch processing, staged quality control, reporting, and output generation.

Both products are provided as atmospherically corrected hyperspectral cubes covering the visible to shortwave infrared (400–2500 nm) range, together with per-band information (e.g., center wavelength and bandwidth, signal-to-noise ratio), geographic metadata (map projection and georeferencing), and per-scene quality layers.

PRISMA L2D products are distributed as a single HDF5 file containing the hyperspectral cube, metadata, and ancillary layers such as the panchromatic band and quality-mask information. Scene-level sea and cloud percentages are reported in the metadata, whereas the corresponding cloud and sea masks are available in PRISMA Level 1 products [16]. In contrast, EnMAP L2A products are distributed in user-selected formats, with .BSQ commonly used for processing, and are accompanied by separate GeoTIFF metadata and quality layers [17]. EnMAP L2A scenes often already have high geolocation accuracy

because the DLR L1-to-L2 processing chain uses Sentinel-2 reference data; nevertheless, applying the same co-registration workflow to all PRISMA and EnMAP scenes remains useful for multi-temporal spatial consistency.

Figure 1. HyperCoreg workflow. The diagram summarizes the full processing chain used to co-register PRISMA and EnMAP hyperspectral scenes to Sentinel-2 Level-2A reference data. It begins with user configuration and sensor-specific preparation of the hyperspectral input, continues through automated Sentinel-2 candidate search and ranking, spectral band pairing, global and local AROSICS-based co-registration, tie-point filtering, quality-control decisions, geometric transformation, validation, and report/output generation. Green blocks indicate workflow functions added by HyperCoreg around the AROSICS core, including automated reference selection, detector-aware preparation, staged quality control, and operational output management. Notation: CDSE—Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem; CLI—Command-Line Interface; CRS—Coordinate Reference System; GUI—Graphical User Interface; GCP—Ground Control Point; QC—Quality Control; SCL—Scene Classification Layer; S2—Sentinel-2; TPS—Thin-Plate Spline.

Sentinel-2 Level-2A products serve as the geometric reference due to their superior geolocation accuracy (approximately 4 m for refined products; [18]). The HyperCoreg pipeline automatically identifies and downloads suitable Sentinel-2 scenes that overlap spatially and temporally with the hyperspectral acquisition to be co-registered. User interaction is managed through a graphical interface where processing parameters can be configured, including the temporal search window for the matching Sentinel-2 scene and its cloud cover threshold, expected accuracy thresholds, and output options. Default values are provided based on extensive testing, but users can adjust parameters to accommodate specific requirements such as scenes with higher cloud cover or stricter accuracy demands (see Table 1).

Table 1. Key HyperCoreg parameters (defaults and typical ranges).

Parameter	Default	Range	Description
days_window	30	1–365	Temporal search window for Sentinel-2 candidates (\pm days).
min_overlap	0.5	0.1–1.0	Minimum spatial overlap fraction between hyperspectral footprint and Sentinel-2 tile.
max_cloud	20	0–100	Maximum allowed cloud cover for Sentinel-2 candidates (%).
max_input_cloud_cover	70	0–100	Skip hyperspectral inputs exceeding this cloud cover threshold (%).
min_accuracy	70	0–100	Minimum acceptable global reliability reported by AROSICS (%).
max_displacement	350	50–1000	Maximum allowed initial shift during global alignment (m).
residual_threshold	25	10–100	Maximum mean residual (m) for accepting a registration.
min_tie_points	10	5–50	Minimum number of tie points required for polynomial warp.
max_s2_candidates	3	1–10	Maximum Sentinel-2 scenes evaluated per hyperspectral acquisition.
residual_mad_factor	3.0	1.5–5.0	MAD multiplier used for residual outlier trimming.
s2_ref_band	B08	B02–B12	Sentinel-2 band used for global alignment.

2.2. Parameter Personalization

This pipeline allows a set of user-configurable parameters to tailor the co-registration accuracy needs, co-registration behavior, and output generation (see Table 1). Key parameters include the temporal search window for Sentinel-2 (`days_window`), minimum spatial overlap (`min_overlap`), cloud thresholds (`max_cloud`, `max_input_cloud_cover`), the minimum acceptable global reliability (`min_accuracy`), and acceptance criteria based on residuals (`residual_threshold`) and minimum tie-point count (`min_tie_points`). Output options (see Table 2) control whether additional products are written (e.g., pre-co-registration images, PRISMA PAN and quality masks, tie-point PNGs, auxiliary GDAL files, and temporary debugging outputs).

Table 2. Output options available in HyperCoreg.

Option	Description
save_pre	Save pre-co-registration image for comparison.
save_pan	Save PRISMA panchromatic band (PRISMA only).
save_quality_mask	Save PRISMA quality mask (PRISMA only).
gen_tiepoint_pngs	Generate tie-point visualization PNGs (global/local).
gen_aux_xml	Generate metadata file.
use_inmemory	Use in-memory processing (faster, higher RAM usage).
keep_temp_files	Preserve temporary files for debugging.
norm_mode	Select normalization mode.
remove_vnir_swir_overlap	Remove VNIR/SWIR overlap bands.

2.3. Data Processing and Sentinel-2 Reference Acquisition

The hyperspectral data are first extracted from their native formats and organized into a standardized spectral band table containing the center wavelength, bandwidth (FWHM), and detector information for each band. This information is stored in a unified structure (the `SpectralBandTable` class), which ensures that the wavelengths are sorted, filters out invalid bands, and reorders the hyperspectral cube accordingly. This enables systematic spectral matching between PRISMA/EnMAP channels and Sentinel-2 reference bands (e.g., by selecting the closest hyperspectral wavelength and averaging adjacent channels to create a pseudo-band with bandwidth similar to Sentinel-2). This hyperspectral-to-multispectral band pairing addresses the challenge of matching sensors with different spectral configurations by selecting PRISMA/EnMAP bands that are spectrally comparable to Sentinel-2 MSI bands and therefore suitable for robust tie-point extraction.

Although the objective of HyperCoreg is geometric, spectral matching is used because AROSICS estimates shifts from spatial intensity patterns [8,19]. The geometric displacement of the scene is common across bands, but the contrast used to identify it is wavelength-dependent. Visible bands can preserve urban texture and some water-land brightness contrasts, NIR bands often enhance vegetation and land–water boundaries, and SWIR bands can strengthen built-up, bare-soil, vegetation-moisture, and urban–natural edges. A single poorly matched band may therefore provide weak or ambiguous correlation peaks in parts of the scene, whereas a spectrally comparable pseudo-band can expose sharper and more stable features for tie-point extraction.

Consequently, spectral resampling in HyperCoreg is a temporary matching step, not a modification of the final hyperspectral product. By combining PRISMA/EnMAP bands that overlap with a Sentinel-2 MSI band [20], the pipeline creates Sentinel-2-like pseudo-bands that reduce sensor-response differences before phase correlation. These layers improve the reliability and spatial density of tie points; the accepted geometric transform is then applied to the original hyperspectral cube, preserving its native spectral bands and metadata.

Sentinel-2 reference scenes are queried from the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE) using temporal and spatial criteria set by the user. The temporal search window is user-defined (default ± 30 days from the hyperspectral acquisition that must be co-registered), and spatial filtering ensures overlap with the hyperspectral footprint. Additional filters include maximum Sentinel-2 cloud cover (default 20%) and product type. Candidates not meeting the minimum overlap requirement are discarded. The remaining Sentinel-2 scenes are then ranked using a composite score that penalizes higher cloud cover and larger temporal distance while favoring larger spatial overlap. In the current implementation, the ranking score is computed as $\text{cloud cover} + 0.5 \times \text{temporal difference (hours)} - 20 \times \text{overlap fraction}$, and the candidate with the lowest score is selected first for processing. For the Sentinel-2 reference, the required spectral bands (i.e., B02 blue, B03 green, B04 red, B08 NIR, and optionally B11–B12 SWIR resampled to 10 m) are ex-

tracted and sampled to a common 10 m grid. The Scene Classification Layer, provided by CDSE for each Sentinel-2 scene, is used to mask clouds, shadows, and other invalid pixels. The Sentinel-2 stack is clipped to the hyperspectral scene extent (with a buffer) to reduce computational load while preserving sufficient overlap for co-registration.

Sentinel-2 Candidate Ranking and Multi-Scene Fallback

To improve robustness in challenging acquisition conditions, HyperCoreg attempts co-registration sequentially until a Sentinel-2 candidate satisfies the user-defined accuracy criteria. If the algorithm is configured to test multiple Sentinel-2 candidates, this will result in longer run-time. However, this approach can substantially decrease the number of failures when the Sentinel-2 image that would be the best temporal match with the hyperspectral image to co-register is partially cloud-contaminated.

2.4. Co-Registration Module

2.4.1. Global Alignment

The co-registration follows a detector-aware, two-stage approach beginning with global alignment to correct bulk positional shifts [8]. For each VNIR and SWIR branch, a Sentinel-2 band is selected as reference (default: B08 NIR for VNIR and SWIR-compatible bands where needed), and corresponding hyperspectral bands in the same range are identified. Since hyperspectral bands are narrower than Sentinel-2 bands, multiple adjacent hyperspectral bands within the Sentinel-2 band spectral range are averaged to create a pseudo-band that better matches the Sentinel-2 spectral response. AROSICS global co-registration is then applied between the Sentinel-2 reference band and the hyperspectral pseudo-band using progressively larger analysis windows (256×256 to 640×640 pixels) and increasing maximum shift tolerances (100 to 350 m). This iterative approach handles initial alignment across scenes ranging from simple to challenging. In this stage, HyperCoreg does not modify the underlying AROSICS correlation engine, but controls how sensor-specific inputs, retry attempts, and downstream filtering are handled. This sequential alignment logic is designed to propagate the geometric correction through multi-detector and multi-product hyperspectral data in a controlled order, rather than applying a single isolated co-registration step that may not consistently handle VNIR/SWIR branches, panchromatic and auxiliary products, or multi-scene outputs. The algorithm evaluates the correlation quality at each iteration and terminates when a reliability threshold is met (default 70%). If global alignment fails with all window configurations and Sentinel-2 candidates, the pipeline can attempt a fallback strategy using local co-registration without global pre-alignment.

2.4.2. Local Alignment and Tie-Point Filtering

Following global alignment, HyperCoreg performs local refinement by collecting tie points across multiple Sentinel-2 bands. For each selected Sentinel-2 band (B02, B03, B04, B08, B11, and B12), the corresponding hyperspectral pseudo-band is created by averaging bands that match the Sentinel-2 wavelength range. This multiband approach leverages complementary information from different spectral regions and increases the spatial density and reliability of tie points. Local co-registration is executed independently for each band pair using a grid-based approach. The image is divided into regular tiles (256 m spacing), and within each tile, the local shift is estimated through correlation analysis. This generates a distributed network of tie points across the scene, each containing the position in both image and map coordinates, the measured displacement vector, and a reliability score indicating the quality of the correlation match. This step addresses local differences in geolocation accuracy across the scene [21].

The interpretation of these local displacement vectors is illustrated in Figure 2. The diagnostic representation links the tie-point displacement estimated at pixel level with the spatially variable distortion pattern observed across a full scene, supporting visual assessment of both global shifts and local warping effects.

Figure 2. Local geometric-warping diagnostic. The figure explains how HyperCoreg interprets local tie points estimated between the hyperspectral image and the Sentinel-2 reference image. Each displacement vector represents the direction and magnitude of the local shift required to align a matched image location, while the spatial pattern of vectors across the scene reveals whether the mismatch is dominated by a nearly uniform global offset or by locally variable geometric distortions. The colors in the schematic background are illustrative and do not encode quantitative classes. This diagnostic is used to visually assess the consistency of the tie-point field before the accepted control points are used for geometric transformation.

The tie points from all spectral bands are merged and the following rigorous four-step filtering process is undertaken to ensure that a good quality tie-point grid is achieved:

- Step 1—Initial Quality Control: Points flagged as unreliable by the correlation algorithm are removed, along with any containing invalid coordinate values.
- Step 2—Reliability-Based Selection: Points are filtered based on their correlation reliability score using an adaptive threshold. The initial threshold (default 75%) is applied, and if insufficient points remain, the threshold is progressively lowered in 5% increments until a minimum number of tie points is achieved or a lower limit (50%) is reached.
- Step 3—Spatial Deduplication: When multiple tie points from different spectral bands fall at the same geographic location, only the point with the highest reliability score is retained. This prevents redundancy and gives preference to the strongest spectral correlations.
- Step 4—Outlier Removal: Statistical outlier detection is applied based on the displacement magnitude of each tie point. The median absolute deviation (MAD) method identifies and removes points with anomalous shift vectors that deviate significantly from the median displacement pattern.

This comprehensive filtering typically reduces the initial tie-point collection to a refined set of high-quality ground control points distributed across the scene.

The adaptive filtering and candidate-retry sequence is summarized in Figure 3. The diagram links the tie-point filtering steps to the decision logic used by HyperCoreg: valid solutions proceed to transformation, whereas insufficient or unreliable tie-point sets trigger testing of the next Sentinel-2 candidate or, when configured, a simpler fallback transformation.

Figure 3. Adaptive filtering and iterative Sentinel-2 candidate fallback. The diagram shows the quality-control logic applied after local tie-point extraction. Candidate tie points are first screened for invalid or unreliable matches, then filtered by correlation reliability using an adaptive threshold, deduplicated when several spectral bands provide a match at the same geographic location, and finally tested for displacement outliers using the Median Absolute Deviation (MAD) criterion. If the retained tie points satisfy the minimum-count and quality requirements, they are passed to the geometric transformation module; otherwise, HyperCoreg tests the next ranked Sentinel-2 reference candidate or, when configured, falls back to a simpler transformation path to avoid forcing an unstable warp.

2.5. Geometric Transformation Module

The filtered tie points serve as ground control points (GCPs) for estimating the geometric transformation model. HyperCoreg first evaluates whether the number and spatial geometry of the GCPs support the preferred second-order polynomial transformation. If the GCP set is sufficient, the polynomial model is estimated using least-squares optimization and used to warp the hyperspectral cube to the corrected geometry.

More explicitly, the local displacement field is first estimated by the AROSICS co-registration core [8,15]. For each matching window i , AROSICS compares a Sentinel-2 reference subset R_i with the corresponding hyperspectral target subset T_i by phase correlation. If $F_{R,i}(u, v)$ and $F_{T,i}(u, v)$ are their Fourier transforms, the normalized cross-power spectrum is

$$C_i(u, v) = \frac{F_{R,i}(u, v)F_{T,i}^*(u, v)}{|F_{R,i}(u, v)F_{T,i}^*(u, v)|'} \tag{1}$$

and the phase-correlation surface is

$$c_i(x, y) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{C_i(u, v)\}. \tag{2}$$

The integer shift is obtained from the location of the maximum of $c_i(x, y)$, and the sub-pixel refinement is derived from the neighbourhood of this peak. The resulting local displacement vector $\Delta_i = (\Delta p_i, \Delta l_i)$ is converted to map units and associated with the corresponding image coordinate (p_i, l_i) and target reference coordinate (X_i^*, Y_i^*) .

The final geometric warp is then estimated from the accepted GCPs. For polynomial order n , HyperCoreg models the corrected map coordinates as

$$\hat{X}_i = \boldsymbol{\phi}_n(p_i, l_i)^T \mathbf{a}, \quad \hat{Y}_i = \boldsymbol{\phi}_n(p_i, l_i)^T \mathbf{b}. \tag{3}$$

The affine fallback uses $\boldsymbol{\phi}_1 = [1, p_i, l_i]^T$, whereas the preferred second-order model uses $\boldsymbol{\phi}_2 = [1, p_i, l_i, p_i l_i, p_i^2, l_i^2]^T$ [22]. The coefficient vectors are fitted independently by least squares,

$$\mathbf{a} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{a}} \sum_i \left(\boldsymbol{\phi}_n(p_i, l_i)^T \mathbf{a} - X_i^* \right)^2, \quad \mathbf{b} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{b}} \sum_i \left(\boldsymbol{\phi}_n(p_i, l_i)^T \mathbf{b} - Y_i^* \right)^2. \tag{4}$$

The residual error used for quality assessment is

$$r_i = \sqrt{(\hat{X}_i - X_i^*)^2 + (\hat{Y}_i - Y_i^*)^2}, \tag{5}$$

reported in metres.

These equations describe the polynomial branch used when the accepted GCP set supports a stable global warp. The fallback behavior is part of the same model-selection step. If the available GCPs are insufficient in number, poorly distributed across the scene, or if the polynomial solution is numerically unstable, HyperCoreg first downgrades the polynomial order where appropriate. If this still does not produce a valid output, it attempts a thin-plate-spline (TPS) warp from the accepted GCPs [23]. In that case, the mapping, fitted separately for the X and Y map-coordinate components, can be written as

$$f(p, l) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 p + \alpha_2 l + \sum_j w_j U(\|(p, l) - (p_j, l_j)\|), \quad U(r) = r^2 \log(r). \tag{6}$$

A final fallback to local AROSICS output can be used when configured. This avoids forcing an unstable higher-order transformation and makes the transform selection part of the quality-controlled workflow. The final warped outputs are written as tiled, compressed GeoTIFF files.

2.6. Quality Assessment Module

Co-registration quality is assessed through residual error analysis by comparing the retained tie-point locations after transformation to their target positions. HyperCoreg computes summary statistics of the residual shifts (e.g., mean, median, RMSE, and a high-percentile residual) and evaluates the spatial distribution of the tie points. Spatial metrics include the convex hull area relative to the bounding box (hull/bbox ratio) and nearest-neighbor distances, which help detect clustered tie-point solutions that may yield unstable warps.

HyperCoreg does not use a single monolithic final confidence score for candidate acceptance. Instead, quality control is applied in successive stages. During global pre-validation, the AROSICS output is parsed to extract reliability, displacement magnitude, and similarity diagnostics; solutions with excessive displacement are rejected, and only sufficiently reliable global solutions proceed to the local stage.

At the tie-point level, retained candidate matches are ranked with a composite `QUALITY_SCORE` computed from normalized reliability, Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) improvement, post-registration SSIM, local error, and absolute-shift terms. This composite score is used to rank and filter tie points rather than to accept or reject the full scene by itself.

HyperCoreg then applies reliability filtering, band-support checks, spatial stratification, and median absolute deviation (MAD)-based residual trimming to avoid clustered or locally inconsistent control points. After filtering, scene-level diagnostics are derived from the retained tie points. The exported `quality_score` is the mean retained tie-point score clipped to the [0, 1] interval, and `quality_tier` summarizes it as High, Medium, or Low. Spatial coverage is reported separately through `spatial_spread_score`, `hull_bbox_ratio`, and `is_clustered`, while residual statistics and optional post-warp phase-correlation checks document post-registration consistency.

Final branch acceptance remains separate from those descriptors: a branch is accepted only when confidence meets `min_accuracy`, the retained local tie points meet `min_tie_points`, and the produced output is valid and non-empty; optional post-warp checks can reject a branch when that rejection mode is enabled.

2.7. Output Items

Starting from the original hyperspectral image (Figure 4a), the pipeline uses a reference Sentinel-2 image (i.e., best candidate: Figure 4b) and generates a co-registered hyperspectral cube in GeoTIFF format. An example of the tie-point selection is shown in Figure 4c, where the displacement vectors capture heterogeneous local distortions across the scene. The variation in vector direction and magnitude highlights areas with stronger geometric mismatch, while shorter vectors indicate locally stable regions requiring minor correction. A report for each scene also documents the complete processing chain, including selected parameters, quality metrics (number of tie points, residual errors), Sentinel-2 scene metadata (acquisition date, cloud cover, product identifier), and processing timestamp.

Optional outputs include the pre-co-registration PRISMA or EnMAP image, co-registered ancillary products (panchromatic band for PRISMA, quality masks, and cloud mask), and diagnostic visualizations such as the displacement-vector plot shown in Figure 4c. These products support quality assessment and enable users to verify co-registration performance. For batch processing of multiple PRISMA and/or EnMAP images belonging to the same multi-sensor time series, HyperCoreg can additionally write consolidated summaries (e.g., an Excel file) that aggregate scene-level metrics across runs, facilitating rapid screening of successful and failed co-registrations.

Figure 4. Cont.

c. Displacement-vector visualization

Figure 4. Examples of the main input and diagnostic outputs produced by HyperCoreg for a PRISMA scene over the Metropolitan City of Rome, Italy. Panel (a) shows the hyperspectral scene before geometric correction, providing the input image to be aligned. Panel (b) shows the Sentinel-2 Level-2A image selected by the pipeline as the geometric reference for image matching. Panel (c) shows the local displacement-vector diagnostic derived from the retained tie points; vector direction indicates the orientation of the estimated local correction, vector length indicates its relative magnitude, and the color legend reports absolute displacement in metres. The three panels allow the user to inspect the input scene, confirm the selected reference image, and evaluate whether the estimated correction is spatially coherent before accepting the co-registered output.

2.7.1. Output Directory Structure

For each scene that has been co-registered, HyperCoreg creates a dedicated directory and organizes all outputs as intermediate files, primary and secondary outputs, reports, and quicklooks (Table 3).

Table 3. Example of the output produced by HyperCoreg for a single hyperspectral scene.

Folder	Example Contents
output_dir/HYP_DATE_CODE/00_inputs/	HYP_DATE_CODE_precoreg.tif
output_dir/HYP_DATE_CODE/01_reference/	HYP_DATE_CODE_Sentinel2_stack.tif
output_dir/HYP_DATE_CODE/02_temp/	HYP_DATE_CODE_GLOBAL.tif HYP_DATE_CODE_LOCAL.tif
output_dir/HYP_DATE_CODE/03_coreg/	HYP_DATE_CODE_coreg.tif HYP_DATE_CODE_coreg.hdr HYP_DATE_CODE_coreg.aux.xml HYP_DATE_CODE_pan_coreg.tif HYP_DATE_CODE_qualitymask_coreg.tif HYP_DATE_CODE_cloudmask_coreg.tif
output_dir/HYP_DATE_CODE/04_reports/	HYP_DATE_CODE_shift_report.txt HYP_DATE_CODE_metrics.json
output_dir/HYP_DATE_CODE/05_quicklooks/	HYP_DATE_CODE_overview.png HYP_DATE_CODE_tiepoints.png

2.7.2. Main and Optional Outputs

HyperCoreg always writes the co-registered hyperspectral cube, exported as a tiled, compressed GeoTIFF (e.g., *_COREG.tif). This file represents the hyperspectral scene after applying the estimated global and local corrections.

Optional outputs correspond to the output options listed in Table 2. Depending on user settings, HyperCoreg can additionally export: (i) pre-co-registration products for visual inspection (e.g., *_pre_coreg.tif); (ii) scene ancillary layers (e.g., *_PAN_COREG.tif and *_QM_COREG.tif); (iii) diagnostic quicklooks such as tie-point visualizations; (iv) auxiliary GDAL statistics files; and (v) temporary/intermediate files for debugging.

2.7.3. Batch-Level Summary

When processing multiple scenes (batch processing), HyperCoreg produces a consolidated Excel summary that records, for each scene, acquisition metadata, the selected Sentinel-2 reference product, tie-point statistics, residual metrics (mean/median/RMSE/p90), and processing status (e.g., SUCCESS, FAIL, or FALLBACK).

2.8. Hardware and Computational Requirements

Based on practical tests, a minimum of 16 GB of usable RAM is recommended for processing typical spaceborne hyperspectral scenes; machines with at least 24 GB are generally preferable for batch processing. This requirement is driven primarily by the in-memory footprint of hyperspectral cubes and intermediate resampling steps, while CPU utilization was not found to be the limiting factor. In the test run for this study, the following specifications were used: 32 GB of RAM and an Intel Core i7 processor (3.90 GHz).

2.9. Baseline Configuration for Performance Benchmarking

For performance benchmarking, we compared the full HyperCoreg workflow with a basic AROSICS-based pipeline configuration. This baseline retained the same AROSICS-based global and local co-registration backbone, but excluded the HyperCoreg workflow extensions that are central to the proposed operational pipeline: detector-aware hyperspectral-to-multispectral band pairing, branch-wise processing and recombination, staged tie-point quality control, and quality-driven candidate acceptance. The purpose of this comparison was not to benchmark against a separate software package, but to isolate the contribution of the additional workflow logic built around the shared AROSICS registration core.

2.10. Testing Dataset

To demonstrate the performance of HyperCoreg under realistic operational conditions, a testing dataset composed of hyperspectral scenes acquired over the Metropolitan City of Rome (Italy) was used. In particular, a multi-sensor time series consisting of 110 PRISMA images collected between 2019 and 2025 and 38 EnMAP images collected in 2025 was used. The full list of images used is reported in the Supplementary Materials. It should be noted that the two single-sensor datasets are numerically imbalanced, but this reflects their different acquisition histories. PRISMA data have been collected over the area of interest for a longer period through more distributed and long-standing tasking, whereas the EnMAP dataset is the outcome of a very recent data tasking exercise. Such a situation is functionally representative of very common conditions in studies relying on multi-sensor data, i.e., datasets with different temporal coverage and distribution. Furthermore, this time series is also representative of a situation that is becoming more frequent, given that PRISMA and EnMAP missions are fully operational and are increasingly tasked by either users, data providers, or space agencies to collect observations more regularly over the

same sites. Therefore, the present research provides a quantitatively robust demonstration of the HyperCoreg performance beyond the simple exercise of co-registering a few images (which has so far been the context for most cases in the published literature).

The choice of the Rome test area is motivated by the environmental characteristics of the imaged scene. The Metropolitan City of Rome is characterized by predominantly built-up land cover classes, with interspersed green urban areas, natural areas and major infrastructure (e.g., airport, runways, motorways). This is a dense urban scenario for which studies relying on hyperspectral data would typically aim to reach at least the scale of a single neighborhood, and thus high geolocation accuracy of satellite images would be required in order to reliably associate the extracted spectral features to the imaged objects on the ground. Additionally, many urban applications require integration of the extracted spectral features with other geospatial data sources (often provided at higher spatial resolution), and misalignments between such different geospatial layers can lead to a non-representative and inaccurate analysis. The dataset was selected to cover a range of scene conditions relevant for the assessment of automated co-registration performance, mainly related to cloud cover variability. In particular, the cloud cover across the PRISMA and EnMAP test dataset spanned from a minimum of 0% to a maximum of 82%. For each hyperspectral acquisition, HyperCoreg queried temporally and spatially overlapping Sentinel-2 candidates and selected a reference scene for evaluation according to the ranking criteria described in the previous subsections.

In the present dataset, PRISMA scenes were downloaded as L2D products with archive GCPs, so their initial geolocation accuracy was already improved relative to PRISMA L2D acquisitions over areas where no such GCP support is available. HyperCoreg would be expected to provide the greatest improvements in the latter situation, where larger initial geolocation errors are more likely. This dataset was selected to evaluate whether the pipeline can still improve geolocation for scenes that already have reasonably good baseline accuracy.

Performance in the Section 3 is reported using the residual statistics produced by the pipeline (e.g., mean residual error), enabling a consistent comparison across acquisition conditions and sensors. These residual metrics quantify internal co-registration consistency relative to the selected Sentinel-2 reference rather than an independent external measure of absolute geolocation accuracy.

In addition, mean metrics computed across the full 2019–2025 PRISMA and 2025 EnMAP datasets are reported (processor versions, PRISMA: 2.06; EnMAP: 01.05.05), with the objective of characterizing HyperCoreg performance and the typical magnitude and variability of scene-level shifts.

3. Results

This section evaluates the accuracy improvements provided by HyperCoreg. Beyond the operational benefits of automation, the analysis tested whether the full HyperCoreg workflow yields measurable gains in final residual error when compared with a basic AROSICS-based pipeline configuration. This comparison should be interpreted as a controlled assessment of the integrated workflow extensions around the shared AROSICS core, not as a claim that HyperCoreg replaces the underlying AROSICS matching algorithm.

For brevity and demonstration purposes, we show an example using only a subset of six images from the entire multi-sensor dataset. Table 4 lists the six scenes, i.e., three PRISMA and three EnMAP images, that were chosen to be representative of different levels of complexity (i.e., cloud cover, illumination, season). Figure 5 shows quicklooks of these scenes over the Metropolitan City of Rome.

Table 4. Subset of six hyperspectral scenes used for the co-registration test.

Sensor	Product ID	Date	Numbering	Cloud Cover (%)	Observation Angle (degrees)	Season	Specific Technical Challenge
PRISMA	PRS_L2D_STD_20191125101753_20191125101757	25 November 2019	A	24.2	13.20	Autumn	Partial widespread cloud cover
PRISMA	PRS_L2D_STD_20201229101250_20201229101254	29 December 2020	B	1.7	6.82	Winter	Partial presence of cloud shadow
PRISMA	PRS_L2D_STD_20220604101451_20220604101456	4 June 2022	C	57.2	13.2	Spring	High cloud cover
EnMAP	ENMAP01-L2A-DT0000161871_20251024T104820Z	24 October 2025	D	40.0	16.8	Autumn	High cloud cover
EnMAP	ENMAP01-L2A-DT0000144330_20250715T102956Z	15 July 2025	E	5.0	15	Summer	Mostly cloud-free
EnMAP	ENMAP01-L2A-DT0000155440_20250926T102305Z	26 September 2025	F	20.0	26	Autumn	Partially clustered cloud cover

The user interacts with the program as follows: Upon launching the toolbox, the user selects either single or batch-processing mode to analyze one scene or a set of scenes, respectively. Next, the parameter personalization GUI opens, offering two levels of parameter selection (basic and advanced) and output preparation (Figure 6). In the basic settings (Figure 6a), the user can configure the key options for the Sentinel-2 (S2) query, as well as the minimum allowed accuracy and residual displacement. The advanced settings (Figure 6b) include options that require more in-depth user knowledge since changing them from their default values without prior testing or knowledge may reduce accuracy or cause failures in scene co-registration. Finally, the output options (Figure 6c) refer to the variety of files that can be generated by the pipeline in addition to the main output.

In Table 5, the mean residual errors are reported for each of the six considered scenes, comparing the full HyperCoreg workflow with the basic AROSICS-based pipeline. Overall, the full HyperCoreg workflow yields lower residual errors for both PRISMA and EnMAP scenes, indicating improved geometric alignment with the Sentinel-2 reference. The largest improvements are observed in more challenging PRISMA scenes (A and C), where the basic AROSICS-based pipeline is more prone to unstable tie-point selection. In Scene B, the residual error remains comparable between the two approaches. The basic AROSICS-based pipeline more readily accepts tie points that are spatially clustered or locally inconsistent, which can lead to distortions that are not immediately apparent from visual inspection of the final product. By contrast, HyperCoreg more often produces well-distributed, internally consistent tie points and rejects unstable solutions through its quality-driven acceptance criteria, leading to a more stable global transformation.

Similarly, the EnMAP scenes (D, E, and F) show consistently lower residual error with the full HyperCoreg workflow (from 13.0 to 9.8 m at 40% cloud cover, from 11.6 to 10.5 m at 5% cloud cover, and from 13.2 to 9.6 m at 20% cloud cover), again indicating improved geometric alignment with the Sentinel-2 reference. As in the PRISMA subset, the relative gain is largest in the more challenging cases (higher cloud cover, i.e., D and F), where the basic AROSICS-based pipeline is more likely to accept spatially clustered or locally inconsistent tie points. Even in the low-cloud-cover case (Scene E), the full HyperCoreg workflow achieves a modest improvement.

Figure 5. Quicklooks of the hyperspectral scenes used for the co-registration test. The left column shows the three PRISMA scenes (A–C) and the right column shows the three EnMAP scenes (D–F) selected as representative examples of the wider test dataset over the Metropolitan City of Rome, Italy. The quicklooks illustrate the range of acquisition conditions considered in the evaluation, including differences in sensor, date, season, cloud cover, and illumination. Scene identifiers correspond to the metadata and complexity descriptors reported in Table 4.

Figure 6. Parameter selection graphical user interface (GUI). Panel (a) shows the basic settings used for routine processing, including the Sentinel-2 search window, cloud-cover constraints, and acceptance thresholds for co-registration quality. Panel (b) shows advanced parameters controlling local matching, tie-point filtering, transformation behavior, and fallback options for more challenging scenes. Panel (c) shows the output-personalization options, where the user selects whether to write ancillary products, diagnostic plots, reports, and intermediate files in addition to the main co-registered hyperspectral cube.

Table 6 summarizes the statistics for the co-registration runs performed on the whole multi-sensor PRISMA and EnMAP time series, i.e., image sample size and the distribution of median scene-level displacements (mean, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation). Overall, the EnMAP dataset shows a lower maximum displacement and substantially lower variability than PRISMA data, indicating a more consistent initial geolocation accuracy of the L2A products and greater stability of processing conditions across the tested

acquisitions, which may partly reflect the smaller EnMAP dataset compared with the PRISMA dataset.

Table 5. Mean residual errors obtained with the basic AROSICS-based pipeline and the full HyperCoreg workflow for PRISMA and EnMAP scenes.

Numbering	Mean Residual (m) (Basic AROSICS-Based Pipeline)	Mean Residual (m) (Full HyperCoreg Workflow)
A	20.0	11.8
B	9.8	8.3
C	50.0	15.0
D	13.0	9.8
E	11.6	10.5
F	13.2	9.6

Table 6. Main metrics derived from the co-registration of the PRISMA and EnMAP datasets.

Metric	PRISMA	EnMAP
Sample size	110 images	38 images
Average of median displacement (m)	12.8	11.0
Maximum displacement (m)	32.7	14.5
Minimum displacement (m)	7.1	7.6
Standard deviation (m)	5.8	1.8

4. Discussion

Integrating the increasing volumes of available hyperspectral data with higher-spatial-resolution imagery and geospatial data is challenging, particularly when large numbers of images must be co-registered. Because each scene may present different issues (e.g., shadows, clouds, incomplete overlap with previously collected scenes, or higher noise), manual or image-specific co-registration becomes labor-intensive, as parameters must be adjusted to achieve optimal accuracy. This challenge becomes even more critical when hyperspectral data are integrated with ancillary Earth observation datasets, particularly when comparisons with ground reference measurements are required. The solutions implemented in the pipeline aim to foster the adoption of hyperspectral data by non-expert users, lowering access barriers to data processing and strengthening the reliability of hyperspectral data. In this context, the present toolbox benefits from the robustness of the co-registration approach provided by AROSICS and extends it with new functions, by implementing hyperspectral-to-multispectral band pairing and selection of optimal Sentinel-2 candidates as reference images and allowing the user to assess co-registration performance both numerically and visually, therefore removing the barriers related to co-registration and its accuracy assessment.

More specifically, HyperCoreg automatically selects an appropriate Sentinel-2 reference scene for co-registration, resulting in significant time savings. Additionally, HyperCoreg allows the user to bypass the limitations related to the fact that co-registration workflows often require substantial coding expertise and GUI-based solutions are frequently available only through proprietary software, which can further limit accessibility for many users.

Beyond ease of use, the results in Tables 5 and 6 highlight the practical value of incorporating a quality control strategy into an automated workflow. HyperCoreg reduces the mean residual error in the most complex cases, where cloud contamination and homogeneous land cover can degrade feature matching and lead to unstable solutions. In these scenes, enforcing constraints on tie-point distribution and rejecting outliers helps to

prevent local distortions from influencing the final transformation. When scene complexity is lower, the improvements are smaller, suggesting that co-registration accuracy becomes limited by sensor-specific factors such as spatial resolution differences, image noise, and residual geolocation error of the co-registration target.

The observed performance gains are consistent with the workflow-level design choices implemented in HyperCoreg around the AROSICS core. HyperCoreg is not presented as a fundamentally new image-matching algorithm, but as an operational end-to-end pipeline built around the AROSICS co-registration core and extended through automated Sentinel-2 candidate selection, hyperspectral-to-multispectral band pairing, sequential alignment logic, and quality-controlled acceptance. Each of these additions addresses a specific technical aspect of operational hyperspectral-to-Sentinel-2 co-registration. Automated Sentinel-2 candidate selection addresses the challenge of identifying a suitable, reliable reference image without manual screening, while accounting for temporal proximity, cloud cover, spatial overlap, and the availability of multiple possible Sentinel-2 products. Hyperspectral-to-multispectral band pairing addresses the challenge of matching sensors with fundamentally different spectral configurations by selecting PRISMA/EnMAP hyperspectral bands that are spectrally comparable to Sentinel-2 MSI bands and therefore suitable for robust tie-point extraction. Sequential alignment logic addresses the challenge of propagating the geometric correction through multi-detector and multi-product hyperspectral data in a controlled order, rather than applying a single isolated co-registration step that may not consistently handle VNIR/SWIR, panchromatic, auxiliary, or multi-scene outputs. Finally, quality-controlled acceptance addresses the challenge of avoiding the propagation of unreliable corrections by evaluating the number, reliability, residual displacement, spatial distribution, and post-registration consistency of tie points before accepting or rejecting a candidate co-registration. To our knowledge, these methodological aspects are not specifically addressed by AROSICS alone or by previously developed hyperspectral co-registration workflows.

From an operational perspective, automation is an essential factor when working with large-scale data. When processing many hyperspectral scenes, the time required to identify an appropriate reference image, tune parameters, and verify outputs can be extensive, which this pipeline directly addresses. Nevertheless, co-registration run time is strongly influenced by the pipeline's fallback to alternative Sentinel-2 candidates if earlier candidates fail to meet the acceptance criteria. Reducing the number of tested candidates can therefore decrease processing time; however, it can also increase the likelihood of failure in difficult scenes where the first temporal match may not be suitable.

HyperCoreg is expected to be particularly beneficial for applications where data integration is a primary objective. Despite the strong potential of spaceborne hyperspectral imaging in urban applications, the adoption of these data remains comparatively limited compared with natural settings [24], showing how the operational use of spaceborne hyperspectral data in this field is still emerging. A key requirement for supporting these applications is data integration/fusion and multi-temporal monitoring capabilities, both of which depend on reliable geolocation accuracy across sensors and dates. In this context, quality-controlled co-registration is a fundamental prerequisite for integrating hyperspectral products with other sources.

Nevertheless, some limitations remain and can be addressed in future developments. Pipeline performance can degrade when the overlap with the reference scene is small, when persistent cloud cover leaves too few valid tie points or leads to overly clustered tie points, or when the scene lacks sufficient texture to perform spectral correlation. In addition, broader validation across diverse landscapes should also be performed in the future.

Integrating alternative reference datasets and adaptive parameter-selection strategies may also improve robustness in low-texture scenes.

Topography can also affect the interpretation of co-registration residuals [25–27]. Even when both products are orthorectified, residual relief displacement may remain if the hyperspectral image and the Sentinel-2 reference were acquired with different viewing geometries or processed with different terrain models. In high-relief areas, apparent shifts can become spatially structured along slopes, aspects, ridges, valleys, or terrain discontinuities, increasing local residuals and making them less representative of a purely horizontal geolocation error. The present workflow mitigates the propagation of such effects through spatially distributed tie-point filtering, outlier rejection, and model-selection checks, but it does not explicitly model terrain-dependent parallax because no DEM-derived elevation, slope, or aspect term is included in the residual analysis. Therefore, the residual metrics reported here should be interpreted as indicators of internal co-registration consistency relative to the selected Sentinel-2 reference. Future developments could stratify residuals by DEM-derived elevation, slope, and aspect, or flag high-relief zones where topographic parallax may contribute to local residual patterns.

5. Conclusions

This work presented HyperCoreg, an automated and operational pipeline for co-registering PRISMA and EnMAP hyperspectral imagery to Sentinel-2. HyperCoreg does not replace the AROSICS image-matching engine; instead, it provides an operational, sensor-aware workflow around that core. The pipeline addresses two key bottlenecks in hyperspectral analysis at scale: the need for reliable geometric alignment with higher-resolution references and the difficulty of achieving consistent results across heterogeneous scenes without extensive manual tuning. HyperCoreg combines automated Sentinel-2 candidate selection, hyperspectral-to-multispectral band pairing, sequential alignment logic, robust tie-point filtering, and quality-controlled acceptance to improve the stability and reproducibility of the estimated geometric transformation.

The performance was assessed on a long multi-sensor time series of PRISMA and EnMAP scenes over the Metropolitan City of Rome, spanning a wide range of cloud-cover, illumination, and seasonal conditions. The results demonstrate that this pipeline consistently reduces the mean residual error in the most challenging cases compared with the controlled basic AROSICS-based pipeline.

Beyond accuracy, HyperCoreg is designed to be operationally useful and to favor applications of hyperspectral spaceborne imagery, especially when high geolocation accuracy is needed, such as in urban contexts. Support for both single-scene and batch processing, together with scene-level reports and optional diagnostic outputs, improves transparency and reproducibility and reduces the time required to gather well-suited reference scenes, tune parameters, and validate the results. This facilitates the construction of well-aligned hyperspectral datasets that can be integrated with other sources of information. As hyperspectral spaceborne remote sensing continues to grow, the development of pipelines such as HyperCoreg is essential to move from theoretical and experimental analyses of these data to operational and downstream applications.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/geomatics6030047/s1>, File S1: Full list of PRISMA and EnMAP hyperspectral scenes used in the testing dataset.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

AROSICS	Automated and Robust Open-Source Image Co-Registration Software
ASI	Agenzia Spaziale Italiana/Italian Space Agency
BSQ	Band Sequential
CDSE	Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem
CLI	Command-Line Interface
CRS	Coordinate Reference System
DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt/German Aerospace Center
EnMAP	Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program
ESA	European Space Agency
EXPERT	Reaching Excellence in Hyperspectral Remote Sensing
FWHM	Full Width at Half Maximum
GCP/GCPs	Ground Control Point(s)
GDAL	Geospatial Data Abstraction Library
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format version 5
MAD	Median Absolute Deviation
MSI	Multispectral Imaging
NIR	Near Infrared
PAN	Panchromatic
PRISMA	PRecursore IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa
QC	Quality Control
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
S2	Sentinel-2
SCL	Scene Classification Layer
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index Measure

SWIR	Short-Wave Infrared
TIFF	Tagged Image File Format
TPS	Thin-Plate Spline
VNIR	Visible and Near Infrared

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